

THE PHYSICOCHEMICAL AND TEXTURAL CHARACTERISTICS OF CATALYSTS IN THE CATALYTIC AROMATIZATION REACTION OF PROPANE- BUTANE FRACTIONS

Kholliyev Shamsiddin Xudoybediyvich
Samarkand State University

Normuminov Abdulatif O'ralovich
Samarkand State University
E-mail: Propan-butan-fraksiyasi@mail.ru

ABSTRACT

To examine the catalytic aromatization reaction of propane-butane fraction $(\text{MoO}_3)_x \cdot (\text{ZnO})_y \cdot (\text{ZrO}_2)_z$ in the mesoporous catalyst, this experiment was conducted under the following optimal conditions: when 1.0 mass% Zrnanopowders were added to the mesoporous catalyst $(\text{MoO}_3)_x \cdot (\text{ZnO})_y \cdot (\text{ZrO}_2)_z$ containing the flow differential reactor, $V_{\text{kat}} = 1.0 \text{ cm}^3$, the size of catalyst granules 0.5-1.0 mm, the temperature 450-650°C, $P = 0.1 \text{ MPa}$, volumetric rate of propane 600 h^{-1} . It was determined that both types of acid centers' concentrations and strengths were increased. The textural characteristics of H-bentonite and HSZ were determined as follows: $S_{\text{sol}} = 72.0$ and $170.0 \text{ m}^2/\text{g}$; $V_{\text{porosity}} = 0.107 \text{ cm}^3$ and $0.178 \text{ cm}^3 / \text{g}$ ($V = 0.26$ on water adsorption); $d_{\text{porosity}} = 50$ and 80 \AA ; the distance between the planes $d_{001} = 9.8$ and 17.6 \AA .

Keywords: propane, butane, chromatographic analysis, volumetric rate, high silicon zeolite, catalyst, textural characteristics, mesoporous, acidity center, IR-spectrum, adsorption-desorption isotherm.

Introduction

The most efficient way of recycling propane-butane fractions is recycled them chemically and obtain aromatic hydrocarbons. It is known that aromatic hydrocarbons are primary products in the main organic synthesis industry. At present, the aromatic hydrocarbons are processed from recycling liquid products of oil, catalytic reforming and pyrolysis processes.

Changing in the petrochemical complex raw material base are leading to a shortage of these hydrocarbons. Therefore, searching for alternative energy sources to replace petroleum products for obtaining aromatic hydrocarbons remains an important task.

Nowadays the main alternative sources are natural gas and petroleum gases are aromatic compounds. A number of scientists have been conducting research on the catalytic synthesis of aromatic hydrocarbons [1-5]. In those reactions, high-silicon zeolites containing Zn, Zr, and Pt have shown high catalytic activity [2,5,6]. The disadvantage of the catalytic interaction of these systems is that the formation of a certain amount of methane and high molecular weight aromatic hydrocarbons (naphthalene, alkyl naphthalene) are produced as a result of reaction. In this situation the stable shelf life of catalysts is reduced. Majority of researches of obtaining aromatic hydrocarbons from natural gas and petroleum gases take place in one step. Zeolite catalysts, especially those modified with metals and metal oxides, are widely used in petroleum refining and petrochemistry [7-11]. The traditional method of obtaining such catalytic systems is to absorb the metal salts into the carrier and gradually decompose the introduced precursor [12–19]. However, in this method, the modifiers are not equally distributed over the entire volume of the carrier, but modifiers are localized on the surface of the zeolite crystals. Thus the performance of the catalyst deteriorates. Also the acidity centers of the catalyst play an important role in the catalytic activity of the catalytic system. Hydrothermal synthesis is important in ensuring the isomorphic exchange of aluminum or silicon in the zeolite crystal lattice for modifiers. The acidity and textural characteristics of the catalyst are improved due to isomorphic exchange in hydrothermal synthesis. This article presents the results of the study of the kinetic laws of the catalytic aromatization reaction of propane on the catalyst $(\text{MoO}_3)_x \cdot (\text{ZnO})_y \cdot (\text{ZrO}_2)_z$. High silicon zeolite from kaolin was used as a carrier, which was taken from Pakhtachi district (the Republic of Uzbekistan). The purpose of this research work is to obtain a catalytic catalyst containing $(\text{MoO}_3)_x \cdot (\text{ZnO})_y \cdot (\text{ZrO}_2)_z$ and to study its physicochemical and catalytic properties in the aromatization reaction of propane.

Experimental

Zinc and zirconium were introduced into carrier during the hydrothermal synthesis phase. Hexamethylenediamine and citric acid were used as structural agents.

Aqueous solutions of zirconyl nitrate $\text{ZrO}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ and $\text{Zn}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ were used as a source of zirconium and zinc oxides respectively. The synthesis of the catalyst $(\text{MoO}_3)_x \cdot (\text{ZnO})_y \cdot (\text{ZrO}_2)_z$ was carried out in a steel autoclave and the temperature was 200-230°C. The catalytic aromatization reaction of propane was studied in a flow differential reactor under the following optimal conditions. $V_{\text{kat}}=1,0 \text{ cm}^3$ the size of the catalyst granules is 0.5-1.0 mm. Temperature 450-650°C, $P = 0.1 \text{ MPa}$, volumetric rate of propane 600 hour⁻¹.

The reaction products were analyzed GC (Svet100M, Russia).(21) chromatography; flame-ionization detector (23); capillary chromatographic column OV-101 (100 m x 0.25 mm x 0.5 mkm) (22); carrier-gas-nitrogen (19). Consumption of nitrogen is 30 ml / min, consumption of hydrogen is (20) -30 ml / min, consumption of air is 300 ml / min. Gas consumption is controlled using the gas preparation unit (17). Evaporator temperature-250°C thermostat temperature in programming mode-from room temperature until 250°C. The detector signal was recorded with a potentiometer KSP (24).

The quality of the synthesized catalysts was controlled by IR spectroscopy and X-ray phase analysis methods. Samples were taken on an IR-Fourier spectrometer (Nicolet 5700) in an area of 2000–400cm⁻¹. The crystallinity of the catalysts was determined by IR spectroscopy [6]. X-ray phase analysis was performed on a DISCOVERD8 (Bruker) diffractometer when the angle range was $2\theta = 10-70$ degrees. The acidic properties of the samples were investigated by the method of thermoprogrammed desorption of nitrogen. Evaluation of the parameters of porous structures and determination of the relative surfaces of the samples was performed on an automated gas-absorption analyzer (TriStar 3020). The specific surface area was calculated by low-temperature sorption isotherms of nitrogen vapors.

The acid properties of the synthesized catalysts were studied in a thermal desorption unit with programmed heating of the sample and registration of the signal from the detector.

The chromatographic variant of programmed thermal desorption consists of the sample of a catalyst with molecules of a probe substance (ammonia) previously adsorbed. It is subjected to heating at a certain speed in the carrier of gas stream (helium).

During desorption, the substance in the gas phase passes through the cell of the katharometer; the signal obtained in this case is recorded and processed using a computer program product. The strength of the acid sites of the catalysts was estimated from the temperature maxima on the thermal desorption curves, and their concentration was determined by the amount of ammonia desorbed at the moment of fixing the desorption peaks, and was expressed in micromoles per 1 g of catalyst. High resolution transmission electron microscopy images were obtained on JEM-2010 and JEM-2200FS electron microscopes (JEOL Ltd.) with a lattice resolution of 0.14 and 0.1 nm, respectively.

Energy dispersive X-ray (EDX) spectra and elemental analysis were obtained in a scanning mode on a JEM-2200FS dark-field instrument (HAADF-STEM) using a JED-2300T spectrometer. The XPS spectra were recorded on an ES300 photoelectron

spectrometer (Kratos Analytic) in the mode of constant transmission energy of the photoelectron energy analyzer. High silicon zeolite (HSZ) derived from activated and enriched bentonite was used in this research work. It was synthesized as follows: mixing 30 g of bentonite in 300 ml of bidistilled water. The suspension was prepared and mixed slowly, at that time the particles of the minerals contained in the bentonite were separated into fractions. At that time the particles of the minerals contained in the bentonite were separated into fractions. The suspension was left for one day. Then the sample was centrifuged at a rate of 7,000 rpm for 5 min. The resulting fraction was dried in the open air at room temperature for 6 h and then at 12°C for 12 h. Following that the sample was activated in 1.5M nitric acid at 80-90°C for 2 h. After activation, 200 ml of distilled water was added to the bentonite suspension and cooled rapidly. The obtained sample was washed several times with distilled water, centrifuged, and dried at room temperature for 12 h and then at 65C for 12 h. Then chemically treated with sodium carbonate in the same order as above. The chemical composition of the sample was analyzed by an energy-dispersion spectrometer and radiographic method with a scanning electron microscope.

Acidic, alkaline and thermal activation of bentonite is a widely used method in obtaining porous sorbents for the synthesis of organic and inorganic substances.

Results and discussion

It is known from the scientific literature that the catalytic properties of modified catalysts are directly related to their acidic properties. The acidity centers of zeolite catalysts are an important factor in determining their catalytic activity, the centers are divided into 2 types: weak acidic and strong acidic centers. Studies have shown that the acidity of the catalyst decreases as soon as the amount of zirconium in the catalyst increases which leads to a decrease in its catalytic activity. The results of the study of the acidic properties of the obtained catalysts are given in Table 1.

Table-1
Acidity characteristics of Zr-Mo retaining zeolites

Catalyst	T _{MAK} , °C		Concentration of acidic centers (mkmol/g)		
	T ₁	T ₂	C ₁	C ₂	C ₃
5,0% Mo/ HSZ	188	390	330	198	528
1,0% Zr-5,0% Mo/ HSZ	195	398	377	240	617
1,5% Zr-5,0% Mo/ HSZ	205	410	355	210	565
2,0% Zr-5,0% Mo/ HSZ	212	400	300	120	420

C₁–weakacidiccenters; C₂-strongacidiccenters; C₃- general acid.

All samples tested have 2 different types of acidity centers

When 1.0 mass% Zr nanopowders was added to 6.0 mass% Mo / HSZ catalysts, the reaction was indicated that both types of acid centers' concentrations and strength increased. For the sample of 1.0% Zr · 6.0% Mo / HSZ, the concentrations of weak acid centers are 377 mkmol/g and the concentrations of strong acid centers are 240 mkmol/g, the properties of the catalyst without Zr were corresponding 42 and 48 mkmol/g higher than the properties of the catalyst with Zr. As soon as the amount of zirconium in the catalyst increases, the concentrations of the acid centers of both types decrease. For example, when the content of zirconium in the Mo/HSZ catalyst increases by 2.0%, the concentrations of acid centers decrease by 120 mkmol/g. Thus, the results of the study of the acidic properties of Zr-modified catalysts to 6.0% Mo / HSZ show that with the addition of Zr to the 6.0% Mo / HSZ catalyst leads to a redistribution of the concentration and strength of the acid centers. As a result, the ratios of the acid centers change, which leads to a change in the acidic properties of the zeolite.

Table 2

Composition of products of catalytic conversion of propane-butane fraction in zinc-molybdenum catalyst treated with zirconium nano powders

W, c ⁻¹	T _{reaction} , °C	X, %	S ₁ , %	S ₂ , %	S ₃ , %	S ₄ , %	Y _{Ap} , %
(MoO₃)_x·(ZnO)_y/ HSZ							
800	550	57	6,1	61.0	2.5	30,4	17.3
800	600	88	6,5	50.5	2.0	41	36.1
800	650	98	7,2	46.4	1.0	45.4	43.6
900	650	97	7,7	40.1	1.6	50.6	49.0
1000	650	95	8,0	33.0	2.3	56.7	53.9
1200	650	93	2,5	28.2	3.2	60.1	55.9
1,0% (ZrO₂)_z·(MoO₃)_x·(ZnO)_y/HSZ							
800	550	73	6,6	47.4	1.7	44.3	32.3
800	600	89	7,0	34.0	1.3	57.7	51.4
800	650	98	8,3	26.3	0.9	64.5	63.2
900	650	98	8,8	22.7	1.2	67.4	65.8
1000	650	97	9,0	20.8	2.5	67.5	65.5
1200	650	92	9,2	16.2	2.8	71.8	66.1

It is obvious from Table 2, the introduction of zinc into a zinc-molybdenum catalyst leads to an increase in the overall activity of the catalyst.

The maximum amount of aromatic hydrocarbons is formed in the presence of a catalyst containing 1.0% Zr. The maximum yield and selectivity of formation of aromatic hydrocarbons in the presence of a catalyst containing 1.0% Zr was observed when the volumetric rate of the starting materials was 500 h^{-1} and the temperature was 650°C and were 65.1% and 71.8%, respectively.

Figure 1 below shows the effect of temperature on propane conversion, yield and selectivity of aromatic hydrocarbons in the catalytic aromatization reaction of propane.

Figure 1. Influence of temperature on propane conversion, yield and selectivity of aromatic hydrocarbons

As can be seen from Figure 1, the conversion of propane begins at 500°C to 600°C and above to form target products -aromatic hydrocarbons.

With the increase in the temperature process, there is an increase in the degree of conversion of propane and the selectivity for the formation of aromatic hydrocarbons, when the reaction temperature is 600°C , it reaches 94% and 37% respectively. Similar temperature dependence of propane aromatization indicators are observed for other Zr containing zeolites carrier.

Physicochemical and texture characteristics of the carrier and catalysts

Adsorption of benzene and water vapor before and after acid activation was studied using the BET method. to determine the porous structural characteristics of HSZ derived from bentonite. The adsorption of benzene and water vapor was measured in a vacuum adsorption device using McBen's quartz scales. On the basis of adsorption-

desorption isotherms, the capacity of the monolayer, the proportion of non-desorbed adsorbate, as well as the specific surface area of the adsorbent for water and benzene vapors were determined.

The textural characteristics of H-bentonite and HSZ were determined as follows: $S_{sol} = 72.0$ and $170.0 \text{ m}^2/\text{g}$; and $0.178 \text{ cm}^3/\text{g}$ ($V = 0.26$ on water adsorption); $d_{porosity} = 50$ and 80 \AA ; the distance between the planes $d_{001} = 9.8$ and 17.6 \AA .

The analysis of the surface structure of the examined bentonite was carried out by scanning electron microscopy. The specificity of the composition and structure of the samples was checked using X-ray diffractometric and thermal analyzes. The comparative surface is determined by thermal desorption of argon with assist of chromatographical method.

Figure 2: Electronic photograph of natural bentonite particles

The adsorption property was studied by the desiccator method in statistical conditions for the desorption of water and benzene vapors. The sedimentation analysis method was used to determine the dispersion content. Electronic microphotographs of the samples are shown in Figure 2.

Figure 3: Electronic microphoto of bentonite samples

a) natural bentonite; b) enriched bentonite; d) sample activated with 0.1 M HNO₃; e) sample activated with 1.8 M HNO₃

Using the method of infrared spectroscopy, the nature of the hydroxy group bonds on the surface with the catalyst component and the composition and properties of the catalysts affect significantly the course of the reactions.

The main properties determining the value of a catalyst are: selectivity, activity, stability and specific surface area. The activity of solid catalysts is determined by the number and activity of active centers on the surface of the holding substance and the structure of the holding substance. Catalyst exploitation is associated with the decrease of its activity (which is associated with a change in the structure of the captive substance) or inactivation of the active sites. Modification of the catalyst with additives increases the selectivity of the process and reduces the formation of coke. Analysis of IR spectra of natural and modified bentonite shows that IR spectra are divided into 2 main areas.

The first is 4000–3000 cm⁻¹ region, which is characteristic of the valence oscillations of OH groups bonded with an octahedral cation. The second is 1400-400 cm⁻¹ area silicate structure bands.

Figure 4. IR spectra of bentonite obtained from different locations:

1-bentonite in Navbahor district of Navoi region; 2-bentonite in Kattakurgan district of Samarkand region; 3-bentonite in Nurabad district of Samarkand region, 4-bentonite in Dehkanabaddistrict of Kashkadarya region.

We examined the IR spectra of inactive bentonite which obtained from different locations (Fig. 5). As can be seen from the figure, a significant change in the relative intensity of the peaks and their positions was observed for bentonites obtained from different sites that were not activated. To increase the sorption properties of the initial bentonite, it was treated with soda and various acids (HNO_3 and H_2SO_4) is shown in Figure 6.

Figure 5. IR spectra of bentonite in Navbahor district of Navoi region after various treatments. 1-soda 2- HNO_3 3- H_2SO_4 .

It is obvious from Figure 6, it is possible to distinguish groups that are characteristic in the spectra, differing in intensity.

Wide line of OH-group of adsorbed water in the area $3600\text{-}3100\text{ cm}^{-1}$, the peak appears to be characteristic of deformational vibration in the area of 1640 cm^{-1}

The area, characterized by the intensity of the absorption lines, appears in the bentonite area of 1450 cm^{-1} treated with sodium carbonate.

This is specific to adsorbed CO_3^{2-} , which is explained by the structural change in the crystalline lattice of bentonite when soda is activated. The lines in the 1030 cm^{-1} field are characteristic of the valence oscillations of Si-O bonds and remain unchanged in all cases, which means that the amount of silicon in the sample remains unchanged when the bentonite is treated differently.

X-ray-spatial analysis was performed to determine the amount of tetragonal and monoclinic forms in the zirconium (IV) oxide content of the synthesized samples.

Modification of zirconium hydroxide with MoO_4^{2-} ions allows the formation of a metastable tetragonal form of zirconium (IV) oxide. The monoclinic form of

zirconium (IV) oxide is catalytically inactive in targeted reactions, its presence in the catalytic system leads to a decrease in the effectiveness of $\text{MoO}_4^{2-}/\text{ZrO}_2$.

Conclusion

Thus, the catalytic aromatization reaction of the propane-butane fraction $(\text{MoO}_3)_x(\text{ZnO})_y(\text{ZrO}_2)_z$ was selected as a result of the process under the following optimal conditions: When 1.0 mass% Zr nanopowders are added to a mesocellular catalyst containing flow differential reactor, $V_{\text{kat}} = 1.0 \text{ cm}^3$, size of catalyst granules 0.5-1.0 mm, temperature 450-650°C, $P = 0.1 \text{ MPa}$, volumetric rate of propane 600 h^{-1} . It has been conformed to increase the concentrations and strength of both types of acid centers.

The textural characteristics of H-bentonite and HSZ were determined as follows: $S_{\text{sol}} = 72.0$ and $170.0 \text{ m}^2/\text{g}$; and $0.178 \text{ cm}^3/\text{g}$ ($V = 0.26$ on water adsorption); $d_{\text{porosity}} = 50$ and 80 \AA ; the distance between the planes $d_{001} = 9.8$ and 17.6 \AA .

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